

INVERTED CLASSROOM STRATEGIES AS A GATEWAY FOR AN ENHANCED SCIENCE PROCESS SKILLS IN A BLENDED LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

Quality education is one of the missions of the Department of Education. Many learning modalities were shared to address the educational needs of students even in an educational paradigm shift because of pandemic. In line with this, flexible strategies were utilized in the blended distance learning class environment. Hence, this study measures the effectiveness of inverted classroom strategies of Grade 8 students in enhancing their science process skills and to find out if there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of students as to their learning environments. Using an experimental research design, pre-test, and post-test assessments, learning environment questionnaire, and lesson exemplars undergone reliability and validity, were utilized. To identify the difference between the scores of the respondents, frequency count and mean gain score were used. To determine the significant difference between the pre and post test scores of students when exposed to inverted classroom strategies, and the learning environments, t-test was employed. Results revealed that science process skills were enhanced differently in every exposure to inverted classroom strategies. In discussion-oriented strategy, all skills were improved but, observing skill of students remains in a level of “Moving towards Mastery”. In role reversal 2.0 strategy, only inferring skill of learners was not enhanced based on their post-test scores. In standard inverted classroom, all science process skills reached “Mastery” level except for the skills of inferring, observing, and predicting. Furthermore, there is no specific learning environment to learners has a significant difference in learning Science. It can be inferred that science process skills like classifying, communicating, inferring, measuring, observing, and predicting can be improved using inverted classroom strategies such as discussion-oriented, role reversal 2.0, and standard inverted classroom. The exploration of other inverted classroom strategies can be employed in order to achieve a fully developed science process skill.

Keywords: experimental research, inverted classroom strategies, flipped classroom strategies, science process skills, blended distance learning environment, grade 8, Philippines